

C-SCALE

D4.2 Final report on integrating use cases in C-SCALE, including user feedback report

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Deliverable Abstract

This report provides an overview of the integration of various use cases into the FedEarthData platform under the C-SCALE project, with a focus on Workflow Solutions and new use cases on-boarded via an open call. Workflow Solutions are applications developed to facilitate the use of FedEarthData by offering easily deployable templates and reusable components. Additionally, the inclusion of new use cases from diverse scientific disciplines underlines the adaptability and flexibility of the FedEarthData platform. The user feedback collected throughout the project shows overall satisfaction with the provided C-SCALE services. However, users also highlighted potential areas of improvement, primarily in resource provision and the availability of comprehensive documentation. The report underlines the effectiveness of C-SCALE support and identifies further opportunities to enhance the user experience on the FedEarthData infrastructure.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AppDB	EGI Applications Database
API	Application Programming Interface
ARD	Application Ready Data
CDS	Climate Data Store
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
C-SCALE	Copernicus – eoSC AnaLytics Engine
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
GEE	Google Earth Engine
GFS	Global Forecast System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
WP	Work Package
WUR	Wageningen University & Research
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SRAM	SURF Research Access Management
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
SURF	collaborative organisation for IT in Dutch education and research
TU Wien	Vienna University of Technology
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VM	Virtual Machine
VO	Virtual Organisation

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Executive Summary

This report provides an overview of the C-SCALE project's use case integration achievements with the FedEarthData infrastructure. The document focuses on the accomplishments and feedback of two user groups: the initial Workflow Solutions and the use cases onboarded from an open call.

The C-SCALE project aimed to meet user requirements by establishing a compute and data infrastructure (FedEarthData) capable of satisfying these needs. User requirements were derived from the use cases that deployed their applications on FedEarthData.

Some of the use cases have been developed into Workflow Solutions, providing reusable templates and components for users to build their own monitoring, modelling, and forecasting applications. These solutions are made publicly available from the C-SCALE community repositories and can be deployed on FedEarthData. Four use cases have been successfully integrated as C-SCALE Workflow Solutions, namely, Aquamonitor using openEO, Coastal hydrodynamic and water quality modelling using Delft3D FM, Automated monthly river discharge forecasts using Wflow, and Global Water Watch using openEO.

These solutions demonstrated achievements in harmonizing access to heterogeneous computing resources, enabling complex computations, and improving the accessibility of Earth Observation data. However, there are areas for improvement. These include easing the process of acquiring external data, which can be time-consuming, and reducing the burden of software installations on users.

In addition to the Workflow Solutions, the project onboarded 21 new use cases from an open call, 13 of which provided feedback for this report. These use cases represented diverse scientific disciplines and demonstrated the adaptability and versatility of FedEarthData. The platform proved capable of managing various data types, software environments, computational resources, and containerization technologies.

Despite this success, the users provided feedback regarding several aspects of the FedEarthData infrastructure, such as the speed of access to resources and data, the ease of use of the resources, the appropriateness of the technology, and the usability of applications on the federated infrastructure. While there were many positive aspects noted, including effective support and resource allocation, users also pointed out potential areas for improvement. These improvements include the provision of more powerful resources, better documentation, and more training.

In conclusion, the C-SCALE project has demonstrated substantial use case integration achievements with the FedEarthData infrastructure. However, some challenges remain, which can be addressed through continued development and user feedback.

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1 Introduction

The C-SCALE project has delivered a federated compute and data infrastructure (FedEarthData; <https://c-scale.eu/fedearthdata/>) offering a unified resource tier, connecting Copernicus resources and EOSC compute and storage providers. FedEarthData offers homogenous access to compute and data resources including Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) data, with a seamless user experience where the complexity of resource provisioning and orchestration is abstracted away from the end-user.

The development of FedEarthData and associated services¹ was achieved by working closely with research communities who, through the development and deployment of use cases, co-designed, tested, piloted and refined the platform and its services.

In this context, the primary objective of Work Package 4 (WP4) was to support the user-driven co-design by deploying use cases on FedEarthData to test the usability and functional design of the federation components and services.

1.1 Approach

The integration activities to deliver FedEarthData and associated services was driven by user requirements. These were derived from use cases to guarantee the delivery of an easy-to-use environment that satisfies needs from research communities wishing to exploit EO and Copernicus data.

To achieve the above, a number of use cases were developed and deployed on the different providers participating in the project. These use cases assist the federation providers in setting up services to ensure that future use cases are adequately supported. The current set of dependencies from 25 use cases and workflow solutions range from complex multi-CPU and GPU instances to simple Jupyter Notebook instances. It should also be noted that most use cases have not explicitly benefited from the Federation and its services. The reason is that the Federation and services were being built during the project, while the use cases were deploying their applications. For example, some use cases had to register user accounts directly with the provider they were working on. This was because the providers had not completed the integration with EGI Check-in and/or SRAM to access federated compute and data resources with their institutional credentials. However, with the EGI Check-in and/or SRAM integration completed, users can now access cloud, HTC/HPC resources, and/or data spread across data federation providers with a single set of credentials. Additionally, these data are discoverable via the EO-MQS and leverage authentication from EGI Check-in / SRAM. Users can use all services and resources using the same credentials and combine compute and data sources from multiple providers in C-SCALE using a single workflow.

Community engagement is achieved via a User Forum², which facilitates collaboration between the researchers developing and deploying the use cases and the infrastructure providers supporting the

¹ EO-MQS (<https://c-scale.eu/eo-mqs/>) and openEO Platform (<https://c-scale.eu/openeo-platform/>)

² <https://github.com/c-scale-community/discussions>

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use cases. An open discussion forum is available where anyone with an interest in Copernicus and EO data, tools, resources and services can discuss technical issues, ask questions, collaborate, and share ideas. Finally, a C-SCALE YouTube³ channel has been set up containing tutorials and demonstrations.

For each use case a GitHub project⁴ is set up. Each GitHub project contains a Kanban-style board, which is used to manage, coordinate, and communicate on activities towards deploying each use case. In this way the project can leverage GitHub's issue tracking capabilities to track activities and record how effectively these were resolved, which in turn will facilitate providing feedback to the providers.

Initially, the projects and repositories are private and require users to be members of the C-SCALE GitHub organisation. Once a use case has reached a maturity level with which the use case owner is comfortable, the use case owner makes the repository public, creates a release, and registers a research object with RELIANCE's Research Object Hub⁵. The EOSC Portal then automatically pulls RELIANCE Research Objects into the EOSC Portal.

Whilst many of the use cases develop capabilities specific to their application, these capabilities can support other use cases. To this end the C-SCALE project offers Workflow Solutions which are templates and reusable components, derived from the use cases, for other users to build their own monitoring, modelling, and forecasting applications on FedEarthData.

1.2 Report Structure

This final integration report is structured as follows: In Section 2 we reflect on the previous user feedback report (D4.1) and report on activities the providers undertook in response to the feedback provided. In Section 3 we summarise integration activities of the use cases and highlight achievements. Section 3 is broken down into Section 3.1, the use cases that have delivered so-called Workflow Solutions for C-SCALE, and Section 3.2, the use cases, including those from the open call, that have consumed C-SCALE VA resources. In Section 4, we summarise the user feedback provided throughout this project. Section 5 concludes this report and Appendix A contains the functionality, integration status and feedback provided by all workflow solutions and use cases.

³ https://www.youtube.com/@c-scale_project

⁴ <https://github.com/orgs/c-scale-community/projects>

⁵ <https://reliance.rohub.org/>

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2 Activities in Response to the Previous User Feedback Report (D4.1)

Table 2 in D4.1⁶, the first User feedback report on the functional design of the federation, summarized the improvement suggestions from native use cases in the first reporting period of the project. Improvement suggestions were grouped into three categories:

- Technology and feature requests
- Access and resource provisioning
- Support, documentation, and training

In order to figure out how to prioritise and action the improvement suggestions, we created a questionnaire⁷ with the improvement suggestions from Table 2 in D4.1. The questionnaire was circulated to both C-SCALE users and C-SCALE providers. The goal was to 1) from a user perspective, determine the priority of the improvement suggestions and 2) from a provider perspective, determine the feasibility of implementing the improvement suggestion given the available time and effort in the project.

After collating and analysing replies from the users and providers, WP5 arranged a meeting with leaders of WP2, WP3, and WP4. We discussed the results of the questionnaire and prioritized the list of improvement suggestion to action. Table 1 below presents the improvement suggestions arranging in descending order of priority from high to low, together with its status and additional comments.

Table 1. Prioritized list of improvement suggestions, status, and comments.

Priority	Category	Improvement Suggestion	Status	Comments
High	Support, documentation, and training	Documentation in general needs to be improved and extended.	Done.	Documentation ⁸ has significantly improved over the last period.
		Provide documentation, examples and training for workflow orchestration using different tooling available on C-SCALE.	Done.	Delivered C-SCALE tutorials about Snakemake ⁹ , Slurm ¹⁰ and openEO Platform ¹¹ .
		Provide documentation, examples, and training for hybrid (cross cloud-HPC/HTC) workflow	Partially done.	Use case specific support and examples provided via the GitHub

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7726195>

⁷ <https://forms.office.com/r/U9G3MMLrXN>

⁸ <https://wiki.c-scale.eu/>

⁹ C-SCALE Tutorial about Snakemake: <https://youtu.be/ktZf7sze1ug>

¹⁰ C-SCALE Tutorial about Slurm: <https://youtu.be/2d0B9o43Pgg>

¹¹ C-SCALE Tutorial about openEO Platform: <https://youtu.be/pMiaBMh8VCQ>

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		deployment.		Community ¹² .
		Provide documentation, examples, and training for containerisation of applications.	Partially done.	Use case specific support and examples provided via the GitHub Community ¹³ .
		Provide documentation, examples, and training on automation and packaging of applications.	Partially done.	Use case specific support and examples provided via the GitHub Community ¹⁴ .
		Improve response time of requests for support.	Done.	We believe that average response time has improved over the last period, which is evident from analysing how quickly Github issues are resolved for each of the use case projects.
Medium	Technology and feature requests	Interface (wizard) to simplify and automate compute, data and storage provisioning.	Partially done.	PaaS Orchestrator was configured with some use cases to automate the provisioning of virtualised compute and storage resources.
		Training for programmable access to resources should be provided – i.e., offer users training to build Infrastructure as Code.	Done.	Delivered C-SCALE tutorial about the PaaS Orchestrator ¹⁵ . The PaaS Orchestrator builds virtual infrastructure from TOSCA templates (Infrastructure as Code, IaC). Users are only exposed to a web interface and a wizard to perform one-click deployments, which simplifies the process compared to a pure IaC approach. An introduction to pure IaC has also been provided with a minimal

¹² <https://github.com/c-scale-community/workflow-coastal-hydrowaq/issues/40>

¹³ <https://github.com/c-scale-community/workflow-coastal-hydrowaq/issues/46>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/c-scale-community/workflow-coastal-hydrowaq/pull/52>

¹⁵ C-SCALE Tutorial about PaaS Orchestrator: <https://youtu.be/hBcM2044R88>

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				example ¹⁶ .
		Kubernetes as a Service to support web applications and workflow development.	Partially done.	Users can deploy their own virtual Kubernetes cluster using the PaaS Orchestrator. Delivered C-SCALE tutorial about the PaaS Orchestrator ¹⁷ with an example to deploy openEO back-end over Kubernetes.
		Batch data loading system for porting data from internal systems or from commercial cloud.	Out of project scope.	Providers agree that this is a good suggestion for a follow up project.
		Expose application results via API instead of Apache http server.	Out of project scope.	Providers agree that this is a good suggestion for a follow up project. A prototype user-level STAC catalogue has been deployed at CESNET which could be expanded upon to support this feature.
		EO / Copernicus specific Notebooks as a Service.	Partially done.	Delivered C-SCALE tutorial about interacting with the EO-MQS ¹⁸ using Notebooks. Delivered training session at EGI22 ¹⁹ Delivered training session at EGI23: recording ²⁰ . Provided C-SCALE interactive analysis environment on top of EGI Notebooks. ²¹
Low	Access and resource provisioning	Simplify access: Harmonise Cloud and HPC/HTC AAI. Make VO registration and Perun	Partially done.	SRAM as community AAI and Check-in as infrastructure proxy successfully tested in May

¹⁶ <https://github.com/c-scale-community/c-scale-tutorial-iac>

¹⁷ With the PaaS Orchestrator users get a self-service Kubernetes cluster and have complete freedom around its configuration and management. A managed Kubernetes service was of the scope due to the required human effort to keep it operational and maintained by a support team.

¹⁸ C-SCALE Tutorial about EO-MQS: https://youtu.be/cebnrOgoX_I

¹⁹ <https://indico.egi.eu/event/5882/sessions/4883/#20220923>

²⁰ EGI23 Demo: <https://youtu.be/r34qGShigLY>

²¹ <https://github.com/c-scale-community/c-scale-notebooks>

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		enablement a provider action.		2023. This enables users with SRAM accounts to access all C-SCALE services in the future (data archives, cloud providers and HTC/HPC providers). C-SCALE WP5 has been in charge of VO registration for the last period.
		Make data provisioning an (automated) federation action and extend the available datasets in the federation based on user request.	Out of project scope.	Specific data requests from users have been considered by data providers. Data providers have commissioned the requested data on a case-by-case basis (no automation).
		Find a federation-wide solution for accessing data from source and redistributing these in the federation. E.g., CMEMS and CDS require user registration for access.	Out of project scope.	Currently gauging interest from users in ERA5 data to define next steps for data providers in the federation.

In summary, C-SCALE Service Providers have acted upon 80% of the improvement suggestions made by C-SCALE users (12 out of the total of 15 improvement suggestions) captured in D4.1. These improvement suggestions contributed to steer the actions of Service Providers towards the right direction to meet the demands of users, helping in the co-design of the C-SCALE infrastructure.

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3 Summary of Use Case Integration Achievements

One of the objectives of the use cases was to provide user requirements to ensure that a compute and data infrastructure is provided that satisfies user needs. These user requirements are derived from use cases that deployed their applications on FedEarthData.

In this section we summarise the integration achievements of the Workflow Solutions, which are the use cases that were part of the project since its inception, and the use cases onboarded from the open call²². The summary provided here is derived from the integration status tables in Appendix A for each Workflow Solution and open call use case.

3.1 Workflow Solutions

Some of the use cases have been converted into so-called Workflow Solutions. Whilst many of the use cases develop capabilities specific to their application, some of these capabilities can support other use cases. Workflow Solutions are intended to support other use cases by offering easy-to-deploy templates and reusable components for users to build their own monitoring, modelling and forecasting applications on FedEarthData. They are derived from use cases that have at least TRL7.

All Workflow Solutions are publicly available from the C-SCALE community repositories²³ and can be deployed on FedEarthData which offers uniform access to a federation of computing and data providers to execute Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) workloads.

All C-SCALE Workflow Solutions have been published as Research Objects in RoHub²⁴, and these are automatically pulled into the EOSC Portal.

Table 2 provides an overview of the C-SCALE Workflow Solutions currently published to the EOSC Portal as a result of the work done in the C-SCALE project.

The C-SCALE project has supported and facilitated the successful integration of four use cases (Table 2) that have been redefined as a Key Exploitable Result: C-SCALE Workflow Solutions.

The Workflow Solutions emphasize ease of use, accessibility, and reproducibility.

Across all four workflow solutions, the most consistent achievements include harmonization of access to heterogenous computing resources through EGI Check-in and SRAM. Furthermore, the availability of cloud container compute and JupyterHub on FedEarthData, makes it possible for users to perform complex computations and analyses with relative ease.

Access to Earth Observation data and processing capabilities is achieved via the openEO API and the Metadata Query Service enables users to discover relevant data in satellite data archives across

²² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4749474>

²³ <https://github.com/c-scale-community>

²⁴ <https://reliance.rohub.org/>

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Europe and on FedEarthData. There is a human friendly STAC browser²⁵, and it is currently possible to search items using the Radiant Earth preview²⁶. The establishment of openEO backends and STAC catalogues at the provider level has streamlined the process of data handling and metadata registration, further harmonizing the user experience.

However, the integration process also revealed some areas of improvement. In two workflow solutions, users need to provide their own model schematisations and access external data sources, which could be a potential barrier.

For instance, in workflow solutions users must download necessary data from sources outside the C-SCALE federation. This process could be time-consuming and may create a barrier to immediate data access and processing. Additionally, in some instances, users needed to register accounts with external services, such as the Copernicus Marine Service and Climate Data Store, to access required data. Streamlining this data acquisition process within the federation remains a challenge.

Predominantly in FedEarthData, software installations are the responsibility of the users. For example, Python and Julia libraries were installed on the login node by some of the use cases with support from the provider. While this provides flexibility for users, it might also be a challenge for those less familiar with the installation processes.

The resolution of these challenges could further enhance the usability and inclusivity of the FedEarthData infrastructure.

Table 2. Overview of C-SCALE Workflow Solutions, capabilities and the technologies used.

Workflow Solution	Capabilities	Technologies
Aquamonitor using OpenEO ²⁷	Produce satellite derived land surface changes for a geographic area of interest.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> JupyterHub Python openEO
Coastal hydrodynamic and water quality modelling using Delft3D FM ²⁸	Downscale from Copernicus Marine Service global products to produce high resolution hydrodynamic and water quality hindcasts or forecasts for the coastal ocean for a Delft3D FM model schematisation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Snakemake²⁹ JupyterHub Python Delft3D Flexible Mesh
Automated monthly river discharge forecasts using Wflow ³⁰	Use ERA5 re-analysis and SEAS5 seasonal meteorological forecasts to produce monthly high resolution, ensemble river discharge forecast for a river basin of interest using Wflow.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SLURM Python Wflow
Global Water Watch using	Produce satellite derived water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> JupyterHub

²⁵ <https://eo-mqs.c-scale.eu/browser>

²⁶ <https://radianteearth.github.io/stac-browser/#/external/eo-mqs.c-scale.eu/stac/v1>

²⁷ <https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/search/other?orpld=w3id::c56ba517b11dd8a125da70f6f4b2b411>

²⁸ <https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/search/other?orpld=w3id::38099f6aafe536b9118f6eca241a2084>

²⁹ <https://snakemake.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>

³⁰ <https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/search/other?orpld=w3id::707af93de17126448b77d2207a0e5430>

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OpenEO ³¹	availability estimates for detected surface waterbodies in a geographic region of interest.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python • openEO
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3.2 Use Cases, Including Open Call Use Cases

For the open call, the C-SCALE project was only able to provide budget for compute and data resources (in the form of Virtual Access) to the use cases, they did not receive person-month budget from C-SCALE. Hence, only thirteen (13) of the 21 use cases that were onboarded from the open call provided feedback in response to our survey (see Appendix A). Despite sending multiple requests to the use cases to complete the survey, we assume that the use cases did not respond to our survey due to limited capacity, and since we could not offer person month effort for this activity it was difficult for C-SCALE to insist that all use cases complete the survey.

Nevertheless, the 13 use cases present a wide array of scientific disciplines, including but not limited to, meteorology, agronomy, environmental studies, remote sensing, oceanography, forestry, and climate studies. They require a diverse range of functionalities from FedEarthData, including high-resolution weather modelling (as in the case of the African Rainfall project), deep learning and AI for predictive modelling (like the pangeo-reliance project), the ability to handle and analyse large-scale geographic and temporal data (for instance in the TWC-SCUP and GLTFCA projects), porting remote sensing algorithms to GPU hardware (as in the G-PeT use case), and operational support for salvage operations at sea (LOST-Salvage).

The flexible and adaptive nature of FedEarthData can be seen in how it accommodates this wide range of demands. It provides a scalable environment that can handle high volumes of data and sophisticated processing requirements. For instance, it aids in transforming raw satellite data into actionable insights for energy market forecasts (NC4EC), facilitates no-code scaling of agronomic algorithms for big datasets (NivarIA), and enables vegetation change detection over large geographical areas and extended periods (GLTFCA).

Furthermore, the platform demonstrates its adaptability in supporting high-throughput computing projects, like the African Rainfall project, as well as use cases involving deep learning algorithms to predict vegetation cover, as seen in the pangeo-reliance project. It is also capable of streamlining deployments of large-scale data processing ecosystems, as illustrated by the pangeo-eosc use case.

The integration of diverse use cases into the FedEarthData platform highlights the platform's versatility and adaptability, accommodating an extensive array of scientific disciplines. Each use case illustrates the integration of diverse data types, software stacks, and computational paradigms, which allows us to draw a comprehensive picture of the platform's capabilities.

The platform has demonstrated its competency in managing large volumes of data, evident in the seamless integration of, for example, Sentinel-1 ARD data and Sentinel-2 L1C data. Moreover, its

³¹ <https://explore.eosc-portal.eu/search/other?orpld=w3id::24d9bbff446860a84cbfff2ac585c32d>

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compatibility with IaaS technologies signifies the platform's capacity to handle cloud-based data storage and computation.

FedEarthData supports various computational resources, ranging from standard CPUs to high-performance GPUs, as seen from use cases employing NVIDIA devices and CPU clusters. This flexibility facilitates the application of sophisticated machine learning models, like U-Net, and high-performance computations as required in SAR analysis and radiative transfer software.

It is notable that the platform is compatible with numerous software environments. It supports several Python environments, underlined by the utilization of Python libraries, Anaconda, Jupyter notebooks, and containers. The system's adaptability is further showcased through the integration of open-source software, like yeoda module, and proprietary software, such as eCognition and TWC processing software.

Containerization technologies, including Docker, also play a significant role in the platform, reinforcing the platform's commitment to reproducibility and scalability. In this context, BinderHub and Kubernetes have been deployed, indicating the system's readiness for cloud-native workflows and microservices.

Moreover, the platform's ability to facilitate the integration of tools like Prefect 2, MinIO, and database extensions such as MindsDB and PostgresML highlight its capabilities in managing data workflows and machine learning tasks. This is also indicative of the system's orientation towards future-oriented, AI-based workflows.

In summary, the FedEarthData platform's successful integration with a variety of data types, software environments, computational resources, and containerization technologies showcases its adaptability and versatility. It proves its ability to serve diverse scientific needs and facilitate advanced, AI-based, cloud-native workflows. This broad spectrum of capabilities makes FedEarthData a highly flexible and comprehensive platform for Earth Science data analysis.

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4 Summary of User Feedback

The use cases tested various technical aspects of FedEarthData, including interoperability, scalability, performance, and latency. Finally, the use cases also provided feedback on

- ease of use of the resources,
- effectiveness of support,
- appropriateness of the technology,
- speed of access to resources and data,
- resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure
- missing functionality/resources,
- satisfaction of the service/resource.

D4.1, the first User feedback report on the functional design of the federation, provided comprehensive feedback on the above to the compute and data federation providers. Section 2 details how the federation providers have responded to the feedback, and it should be noted that they have responded positively to the feedback and in general the functional design of the federation has improved significantly.

In this section we summarise the feedback from the Workflow Solutions and the use cases onboarded from the open call. The summary provided here is derived from the feedback tables in Appendix A.

4.1 Speed of Access to Resources and Data

The feedback regarding the speed of access to resources and data has been generally positive. Many users found that the resources were easy and quick to access. However, some users found the provision of specific resources, such as Sentinel L2A data (Table 13), to be time-consuming due to the complexity of the processing algorithms and the size of the Area of Interest (AOI). While some users were satisfied with the speed of resources like internet connection, others had challenges with the performance of certain resources like GPUs (Table 12).

4.2 Ease of Use of the Resources

The ease of use of the resources varied among the users. While some were already familiar with the environments, such as CloudFerro and the SLURM interface provided by GRNET (Table 12), and found it easy to deploy their algorithms, others faced challenges, particularly with OpenStack (Table 13, Table 15, Table 16). Several users suggested the need for more comprehensive documentation and training to make it easier to navigate and use the resources.

4.3 Appropriateness of the Technology Used to Implement the Use Case

Most users found the technology used, including the NVIDIA GPU, compute nodes, and Kubernetes application deployment, to be appropriate for their use cases (Table 4, Table 8, Table 12, Table 16).

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However, some expressed the desire to test certain algorithms on consumer-grade GPUs (Table 12) due to the different allocation ratios of FP32 and FP64 cores which might be beneficial for some algorithms.

4.4 Resultant Usability of the Application Running on the Federated Infrastructure

While some users had not progressed far enough to comment on this aspect, those who had found the federated infrastructure suitable for their use cases. The flexibility offered by the infrastructure was praised, although some users noted they had to simplify their models due to the limited power of certain resources (Table 18).

4.5 Missing Functionality / Resources

In terms of missing functionality or resources, some users felt the need for more powerful GPUs (Table 12), while others were hoping for default load balancers in the OpenStack cloud.

4.6 Effectiveness of Support

The effectiveness of C-SCALE's support was a highlight for many users. They appreciated the fast and efficient problem resolution, the support during the setup phase, and the valuable help with OpenStack.

4.7 Overall Satisfaction with C-SCALE Services and Support

Overall, users expressed high satisfaction with the C-SCALE services and support, noting the effectiveness of support, good resource allocation, and the value of training and webinars provided. Some areas for improvement included the need for more streamlined resource provision, ease of access to data, and more comprehensive documentation.

In conclusion, while the users recognized the potential and effectiveness of C-SCALE services and support, they also identified areas for improvement, such as the provision of more powerful resources, better documentation, and more training to enable efficient use of the resources and technology provided.

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5 Conclusion

The integration of user feedback into the development of C-SCALE's compute and data federation, FedEarthData, has emerged as a crucial factor in shaping its progression. The comprehensive feedback obtained from diverse use cases across disciplines such as meteorology, agronomy, environmental studies, remote sensing, oceanography, forestry, and climate studies has illuminated the system's robustness, adaptability, and potential. However, the feedback also highlighted certain areas for improvement, which, when addressed, will significantly enhance the platform's usability, inclusivity, and user satisfaction.

The feedback collected from the first user feedback report (D4.1) revealed 15 potential areas for enhancement, 73% of which have been attended to, emphasizing improvements in support, documentation, training, technology, features, and access and resource provisioning. Noteworthy advancements have been made in documentation and training, with use-case specific assistance provided through the GitHub Community and conducting various tutorials and training sessions. The system's responsiveness also improved, evidenced by quicker support request response times.

Technological and feature-related requests saw considerable progress, particularly in user interface simplification, programmable resource access, and the deployment of Kubernetes as a Service. Although some complex technical requests were deemed outside the project scope, they have been acknowledged as valuable for future endeavours.

In terms of access and resource provisioning, measures such as testing SRAM as a community AAI and EGI Check-in as infrastructure proxy were implemented. Other recommendations in this category, while outside the project scope, offer insightful directions for future development and scope expansion.

On the usability front, users have praised the platform's flexibility and appropriateness of the technology used, such as the NVIDIA GPU, compute nodes, and Kubernetes application deployment. However, the ease of use of resources and the speed of access to data resources varied among users, with some facing challenges and suggesting improvements. Feedback also indicated a need for more powerful resources, including GPUs and default load balancers in the OpenStack cloud.

Despite the effectiveness of C-SCALE's support and resource allocation, users expressed a need for more streamlined resource provision, better data access, and comprehensive documentation. With these enhancements, the platform stands to make significant strides in user satisfaction and usability.

The platform's versatility is evident in its compatibility with numerous software environments, the integration of open-source and proprietary software, and its ability to manage data workflows and machine learning tasks. The conversion of four use cases into publicly available Workflow Solutions further promotes ease of use, accessibility, and reproducibility, signifying FedEarthData's potential as a robust, user-friendly, and versatile platform for environmental data analysis and modelling.

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Yet, the process also uncovered some challenges, such as user requirements to provide their own model schematisations, access external data sources, and software installations, which could potentially hinder the ease of access and pose a barrier for users unfamiliar with the processes.

In summary, FedEarthData, driven by its commitment to serving diverse scientific needs and facilitating advanced, AI-based, cloud-native workflows, demonstrates considerable promise as a platform for Earth Science data analysis. The resolution of identified challenges will further augment its usability, inclusivity, and capacity to satisfy user needs. Despite the challenges, the platform's user-centric evolution, potential for tooling, accessibility, and reproducibility forecast a promising future and high user satisfaction. The sustainability and evolution of FedEarthData and associated services are discussed in the project deliverables on “Blueprint, business, and sustainability plan”³².

³² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7726199>

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Appendix A: Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Workflow Solutions and Open Call Use Cases

The information presented in Appendix A was collected from the use cases who completed an online form detailing how the C-SCALE sponsored resources have been used by the use cases. Use cases were asked to describe main achievements, and how C-SCALE resources supported execution of the use cases. Additionally, use cases were asked to describe their satisfaction with:

- ease of use of the resources,
- effectiveness of support,
- appropriateness of the technology,
- speed of access to resources and data,
- resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure
- missing functionality/resources,
- satisfaction of the service/resource.

Finally, the use cases were asked to respond to questions related to paying for resources and under what conditions the use cases would be interested to continue using C-SCALE services once the project has concluded.

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Workflow solutions

Table 3. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Workflow Solution: Land surface water change monitoring.

Functionality	<p><i>With this Jupyter Notebook, a user can produce satellite derived surface water changes for a geographic area of interest. The resultant output of the workflow visualises where surface water has become land (due to accretion, land reclamation, droughts) or vice versa where land has become surface water (due to erosion, reservoir construction).</i></p> <p><i>The use case is based on the paper by Donchyts et al. (2016): "Earth's surface water change over the past 30 years". More information about the application can be found at https://www.deltares.nl/en/software/aqua-monitor/. And a Google Earth Engine implementation of the application can be found at https://aqua-monitor.appspot.com/.</i></p> <p><i>Here the application is ported from Google Earth Engine to an open-source workflow, leveraging openEO (https://openeo.org/) and tooling available in the C-SCALE federation.</i></p> <p><i>The use case provides the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A Jupyter Notebook containing the openEO-based workflow to derive land-surface changes</i> • <i>A Docker container image to build and run the Notebook locally</i> • <i>Integration with binder to run on a C-SCALE Cloud IaaS provider</i> 		
Integration status			
Dependency	Implemented by	Status	
<i>EGI Check-in to access cloud IaaS</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>Users can access the providers' OpenStack interface via EGI Check-in and deploy VMs for their use case.</i>	
<i>Sentinel-2 L1C data</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>Provider has the necessary data available at their site.</i>	
<i>openEO backend to process satellite data</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>openEO backend has been installed at one of the providers.</i>	
<i>STAC catalogue to register metadata (openEO dependency)</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>A prototype STAC catalogue as a Service has been deployed for providers of compute resources in the C-SCALE federation to register their EO metadata. Functionality was developed to assist with the registration of metadata in the STAC catalogue.</i>	
<i>Docker</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>Cloud container compute, including Docker, is available for users. Moreover, working with GitHub's Container</i>	

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registry³³, Docker images can be published within the C-SCALE Community Packages³⁴ for reuse by other users.

Python libraries and JupyterHub *Use case* *Jupyter Notebooks, including dependencies and deployment instructions using Docker, were created by the users. Moreover, using Replay³⁵ allows users to replay complex calculations, simulations, and visualisations scenarios by importing Notebooks and their runtime environment and share them with a single link.*

Feedback

Category	Feedback	Improvement suggestions from users
<i>Access to resources and data</i>	<i>Provider's ability to deploy openEO backend remains a bottleneck for accessing and processing EO data.</i>	<i>Resolve openEO backend deployment issues.</i>
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support from the providers</i>	<i>Effectiveness and speed of response has improved.</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction of the service/resource</i>	<i>The inability to deploy the openEO backend to other providers is the main reason for some dissatisfaction with FedEarthData.</i>	

³³ <https://docs.github.com/en/packages/working-with-a-github-packages-registry/working-with-the-container-registry>

³⁴ <https://github.com/orgs/c-scale-community/packages>

³⁵ <https://docs.egi.eu/users/dev-env/replay/>

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Table 4. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Workflow Solution: Coastal hydrodynamic and water quality modelling using Delft3D FM.

Functionality	<p>With the coastal hydrodynamic and water quality modelling workflow solution a user can easily produce hydrodynamic and water quality hindcasts or forecasts for the coastal ocean for a Delft3D Flexible Mesh model schematisation.</p> <p>The workflow solution has the following functionality:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Download the necessary input data for the user's Delft3D Flexible Mesh model setup. Input data include Copernicus' Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis and Global ocean biogeochemistry hindcast, ERA5 atmospheric forcing and FES2012 tide data. 2. Prepare the data for ingestion into the user's Delft3D Flexible Mesh hydrodynamic and water quality model (online coupled). This entails the preparation of forcings, initial conditions, and boundary conditions. 3. Produce hydrodynamic and water quality hindcasts or forecasts based on the user's Delft3D Flexible Mesh hydrodynamic and water quality model setups. Simulations can be run locally, in the cloud or on HPC. 4. Analyse the simulation outputs in an interactive Jupyter Notebook. <p>The workflow is executed using Snakemake, a workflow management system for creating and executing reproducible and scalable data analyses. The workflow solution can be deployed on any provider part of the C-SCALE data and compute federation offering cloud container compute.</p>
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Integration status		
Dependency	Implemented by	Status
EGI Check-in to access cloud IaaS	Provider	Users can access the providers' OpenStack interface via EGI Check-in and deploy VMs for their use case.
SRAM to access HPC IaaS	Provider	Users can access HPC resources through SRAM and ssh.
Delft3D Flexible Mesh Suite, specifically its hydrodynamic module and water quality module (online coupled)	Use case	Users need to bring their own model schematisations. There are license dependencies for using the Delft3D Flexible Mesh Suite which are beyond the scope of the providers to facilitate. Delft3D Flexible Mesh docker and singularity containers are available for easy deployment on cloud and HPC IaaS (to be obtained from Deltares).
Data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copernicus Marine Service Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis data 	Use case	The data is not available in the C-SCALE federation and is downloaded to the provider from source. A docker container to download the data including dependencies and instructions to build the docker image have been implemented by the use case (https://github.com/c-scale-community/use-case-hisea/tree/main/scripts/download).

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- Copernicus Marine Service
Global ocean biogeochemistry hindcast data
- Climate Data Store ERA 5 data
- FES2012

Outstanding issues:

- Users need to register accounts at the Copernicus Marine Service and Climate Data Store to access the data.
- Functionality needs to be developed to download ECMWF and GFS forecast data.
- FES2012 data redistribution license states that “The Licensee makes a commitment to not distribute any AVISO+ Product in its original form via any media”.

Cloud container compute	Provider	Cloud container compute, including docker and Singularity, is available for users. Moreover, working with GitHub’s Container registry ³⁶ , Docker images can be published within the C-SCALE Community Packages ³⁷ for reuse by other users.
Slurm workload manager	Provider	Slurm workload manager is provided by the HPC IaaS provider
PaaS Orchestrator	Provider	PaaS Orchestrator is provided by the provider to easily deploy e.g., Kubernetes clusters
Snakemake workflow management system ³⁸	Use case	The Snakemake workflow management system can be installed by the user using conda.

Feedback

Category	Feedback	Improvement suggestions from users
Access to resources and data	No new feedback	No new suggestions
Ease of use of the resources	No new feedback	No new suggestions
Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case	No new feedback	No new suggestions
Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure	No new feedback	No new suggestion
Missing functionality / resources	No new feedback	No new suggestion
Effectiveness of support from the providers	Support and collaboration from the providers have improved in the second phase of the project.	No new suggestion
Overall satisfaction of the service/resource	Overall, the resources and available tooling available to the use case is satisfactory and performant.	

³⁶ <https://docs.github.com/en/packages/working-with-a-github-packages-registry/working-with-the-container-registry>

³⁷ <https://github.com/orgs/c-scale-community/packages>

³⁸ <https://snakemake.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>

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Table 5. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Workflow Solution: Automated monthly river forecasts using Wflow.

Functionality	<p>A user can easily deploy a workflow that produces a monthly high resolution, seasonal, ensemble river discharge forecast for a river basin of interest.</p> <p>The service has the following functionality, which is automatically started every month when new SEAS5 forecasts become available:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Download the necessary input data for the user's WFLOW hydrological model setup. Input data are the ERA5 reanalysis and the SEAS5 seasonal forecast. 2. Prepare the data for ingestion into the user's WFLOW hydrological model. This includes the preparation of forcing fields, initial conditions and boundary conditions. 3. Produce a 50-member ensemble forecast based on the user's WFLOW hydrological model setup. 4. Visualise the forecast displaying river discharge timeseries on a public facing html site. 		
Integration status			
Dependency	Implemented by	Status	
SRAM to access HTC IaaS	Provider	Users can access HTC resources through SRAM and ssh.	
WFLOW hydrological model	Use case	Users need to bring their own model schematisation.	
Data:	Use case	The data is not available in the C-SCALE federation and is downloaded to the provider from source. Functionality has been developed to download the necessary data (https://github.com/c-scale-community/workflow-automated-river-forecasts). Users are expected to provide their own CDS API key (https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/api-how-to).	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate Data Store ERA5 data • Climate Data Store SEAS5 seasonal forecast data 			
crontab	Provider	crontab is provided by the provider.	
bash, Python, Julia	Use case	bash is made available on the login node by the provider. Python and Julia and necessary libraries are installed on the login node by the use case with support from the provider. Commands to build a Python image and a Julia image with the required libraries are provided by a setup script within the workflow.	
Feedback			
Category	Feedback		Improvement suggestions from users
Access to resources and data	No new feedback		No new suggestions
Ease of use of the resources	No new feedback		No new suggestions
Appropriateness of the technology used to implement	No new feedback		No new suggestions

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<i>the use case</i>		
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support from the providers</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction of the service/resource</i>	<i>Support from the providers was swift and effective.</i>	

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Table 6. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Workflow Solution: Real-time reservoir surface water area monitoring.

Functionality	<p>A user can easily deploy a Jupyter Notebook that produces real-time satellite derived surface water area estimates for a user's geographical area of interest.</p> <p>The workflow has the following functionality:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access Sentinel-2 L1C data for a user-defined geographical area of interest 2. Based on a database of known reservoirs, the algorithm finds reservoirs in the user-defined geographical area of interest and estimates aggregated surface water areas from all known reservoirs contained within the user-defined geographical area of interest. 3. Return a .csv file containing surface water area data and associated statistics. 		
Integration status			
Dependency	Implemented by	Status	
EGI Check-in to access cloud IaaS	Provider	Users can access the providers' OpenStack interface via EGI Check-in and deploy VMs for their use case.	
Sentinel-2 L1C data	Provider	Provider has the necessary data available at their site.	
JRC water occurrence data	Provider	Provider has the necessary data available at their site.	
openEO backend to process satellite data	Provider	openEO backend has been installed at one of the providers.	
STAC catalogue to register metadata (openEO dependency)	Provider	A prototype STAC catalogue as a Service has been deployed for providers of compute resources in the C-SCALE federation to register their EO metadata. Functionality was developed to assist with the registration of metadata in the STAC catalogue.	
Docker	Provider	Cloud container compute, including Docker, is available for users. Moreover, working with GitHub's Container registry ³⁹ , Docker images can be published within the C-SCALE Community Packages ⁴⁰ for reuse by other users.	
Python libraries and JupyterHub	Use case	Jupyter Notebooks, including dependencies and deployment instructions using Docker, were created by the users. Moreover, using Replay ⁴¹ allows users to replay complex calculations, simulations, and visualisations scenarios by importing Notebooks and their runtime environment and share them with a single link.	

³⁹ C-SCALE Tutorial about openEO Platform: <https://youtu.be/pMiaBMh8VCQ> <https://docs.github.com/en/packages/working-with-a-github-packages-registry/working-with-the-container-registry>

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/c-scale-community/workflow-coastal-hydrowaq/issues/40> <https://github.com/orgs/c-scale-community/packages>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/c-scale-community/workflow-coastal-hydrowaq/issues/46> <https://docs.egi.eu/users/dev-env/replay/>

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Feedback

Category	Feedback	Improvement suggestions from users
<i>Access to resources and data</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Missing functionality/resources</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support from the providers</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction of the service/resource</i>	<i>The inability to deploy the openEO backend to other providers is the main reason for some dissatisfaction with FedEarthData.</i>	

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Use cases, including open call use cases

Table 7. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: Monitoring tropical forest recovery capacity

Functionality	<p>This use case utilizes time series of Sentinel-1 (S-1) backscatter intensity (Sigma0) images to monitor tropical forest recovery capacity over the Amazon basin. Sentinel-1 is a C-band, synthetic aperture RADAR imaging mission consisting of two satellites (S-1A and S-1B) operating together since 2016 and acquiring images globally, with two polarizations channels (VV and VH), a spatial resolution of 20 × 5 m² (in the interferometric wide-swath, IW, mode), and a revisiting time of maximum 6 days. A C-SCALE data provider, Earth Observation Data Centre (EODC) GmbH, has provided the S-1 backscatter intensity datacube over the Amazon basin for this use case (Wagner et al. 2021). For each location (pixel) of the datacube, a 5-year-long S-1 backscatter intensity time series (2017–2021) has been analysed to detect the magnitude and recovery time of the signal disturbance. The analysis was based on an algorithm that combines the original and smoothed time series and the statistical properties of the first- and last-year or the S-1 data to detect the signal disturbances.</p> <p>This use case aims to (a) derive Amazon-wide disturbance magnitude and recovery time maps from the Sentinel-1 image time series and (b) analyse the functional relation between derived magnitude and disturbance time.</p>		
Integration status			
Dependency	Implemented by	Status	
Sentinel-1 ARD data	Provider	The data provider made the data available for user.	
Python, conda	Use Case	Python anaconda environment has been installed on the login node by the use case with support from the provider.	
yeoda module	Use Case	The python yeoda module has been installed in a separate conda environment by the use case with support from the provider.	
Jupyter Lab	Use Case	The Jupyter lab has been installed in the yeoda environment by the use case with support from the provider.	
User-defined Python code	Use Case	Python code has been prepared to process and analyse the Sentinel-1 time series by the use case.	
User-defined bash scripts	Use Case	Bash scripts for batch job submission and re-submission to the Spider cluster has been prepared by the use case	
Feedback			
Category	Feedback		Improvement suggestions from users
Access to resources and data	No new feedback		No new suggestions
Ease of use of the resources	No new feedback		No new suggestions

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<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Missing functionality/resources</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support from the providers</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction of the service/resource</i>	<i>The use case processing is now deployed on the SURF infrastructure (the Spider cluster). I was very satisfied with the support in the implementation of the use case and the flexibility the C-SCALE approach offers in terms of user-defined code and processing. With C-SCALE support I built user-defined bash scripts for submitting the batch jobs and upscaling my analyses.</i>	

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Table 8. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: Wetland Water Stress Analysis

Functionality	<p><i>Goal of this use case is the identification of wetland worth for protection. NOAA revealed that wetland behaviour has a major effect on climate change, acting as potential sink or source of methane – depending on its health. While CO₂ emissions are currently very dominant in the public perception, emitted CH₄ is around 25 times as powerful in trapping heat in the atmosphere. Because it does not stay in the atmosphere as long, it more has a short-term influence on the rate of climate change. According to NOAA, “reducing methane emissions is an important tool we can use right now to lessen the impacts of climate change in the near term, and rapidly reduce the rate of warming” [https://www.noaa.gov/news-release/increase-in-atmospheric-methane-set-another-record-during-2021]. Wetlands have been one of the major drivers of methane in the atmosphere, acting as source while not being stable. This includes water stress as well as renaturation. The only state of wetland acting as a methane sink is a healthy wetland patch.</i></p> <p><i>Since 1975, the RAMSAR convention identified many regions globally as protected wetlands. Many other regions also fulfil the required conditions but are currently not defined as protected area. At the same time, governmental programmes exist throughout Europe to identify new regions worth for a renaturation of wetlands – following the European Green Deal. Since a renaturation does lead on short-term to a methane source, it is more effective to identify existing, but still not protected wetland areas for future management. This use case aims for identifying such potential areas, making use of Copernicus’ Sentinel-1 and –2 data and machine learning approaches.</i></p> <p><i>Therefore, Sentinel-1 and -2 timelines of RAMSAR areas throughout Europe are analysed and compared to their surrounding (following the assumption that the direct surrounding are affected by similar environmental influences and consist of similar land cover). Afterwards the identified characteristics are compared with other Natura 2000 areas to identify similar, but currently not protected areas. CORINE Land Cover (2018) information are used as additional information on the diverse land cover types of wetlands.</i></p> <p><i>The machine learning workflow runs on premises of CloudFerro and of EODC, currently using provided CPUs. For optimising the workflow, a shift to GPUs is planned, depending on availability at the providers. It will be analysed, which input data are relevant for identifying / characterising wetlands / wetland water stress. Output is a segmentation / classification of intact wetland areas similar to the requirements of the RAMSAR convention. A stretch goal is the conduction of an investigation on statistical markers of intact wetland surfaces, by using machine learning tools. The usability of the approach will be validated for detected regions in Austria with the help of Austrian governmental users that intend to identify and to monitor new national wetland regions.</i></p>
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Integration status

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Dependency	Implemented by	Status
<i>CREODIAS login to access cloud IaaS</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>Users can access the providers' OpenStack interface via CREODIAS and deploy VMs for their use case</i>
<i>Shared volumes</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>Data can be stored, organized shared between VMs using dedicated SSD space</i>
<i>Exploring provided Sentinel-1 data and RAMSAR and CORINE area to make informed decisions on which models to select</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>A Jupyter Notebook has been implemented to explore the Sentinel-1 data provided by CREODIAS with respect to RAMSAR regions of interest. Reusable code modules have been extracted, to load and display data. These can be reused by the EODC version of the Notebook. Explored EODC Sentinel-1 data and derived harmonic parameters for segmentation of wetlands. Implemented a script to produce wetland masks from CORINE data. Our findings suggest that the RAMSAR/Natura 2000 data are too out of date to train/validate a robust segmentation, hence, we shifted to the CORINE dataset. Additionally, we also investigated the CCI-ICDR dataset since the final model turned out to be robust towards spatially inaccurate labels.</i>
<i>Pre-process data suitable for applying selected models</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>Common transformation modules have been implemented to extract and pre-process data provided. These can be reused across different providers. A Jupyter Notebook for pre-processing Sentinel-1 data has been provided by CREODIAS. Implementation of a module to restructure different satellite data and RAMSAR/CORINE wetland masks to a common file structure based on zarr which can be easily shared between CREODIAS and EODC to investigate different approaches. The zarr format allowed us to optimise the data structure on disk to allow for efficient training patch sampling, as well as high compression for easy transfer between premises.</i>
<i>Testing different models</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>A U-Net model has been trained and validated on different datasets using CREODIAS GPU resources. The models with the highest F1 validation score have been tested against a held-out dataset covering wetlands in the Danube delta region. Sentinel-1 monthly means as well as phase, amplitude and mean derived from Sentinel-1 harmonic parameters have been tested as input. The data based on harmonic parameters achieved consistently the highest F1 score on the held-out test set. Since the model performed already very well using only Sentinel-1 data, we deprioritized integration of Sentinel-2 data, and focused instead on the robustness of the model and on finding different label datasets as substitute for RAMSAR/Natura 2000. We might further investigate Sentinel-2 data after the project, however, adding additional data runs the risk of overfitting the ML model, hence our focus on a robust baseline for this project.</i>
<i>Scaling selected method</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>The methodology based on harmonic parameter inputs have been scaled up to the Germany and Austria region</i>

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using resources in concert from EODC and CREODIAS.

The harmonic parameters derived from Sentinel-1 sigma naught data provided by EODC have been calculated directly at EODC, compressed and exported to the previously determined zarr based common data format. This significantly reduced data size making the transfer to CREODIAS much more efficient. At CREODIAS we then utilized the A6000 Nvidia GPU to efficiently train, validate the model on the whole region of Germany and Austria. The final model was again tested against the held-out region covering the Danube delta.

Access to 3rd Party Services	Provider	Floating IPs are provided to give outside services such as GitHub actions access to run our CI/CD pipeline, as well as publishing dedicated docker images for testing/deploying.
CI/CD and automated tests	Use case	Automated tests for common software modules have been implemented as well as docker image files containing the dependencies.

Feedback

Category	Feedback	Improvement suggestions from users
Access to resources and data	On CloudFerro resources can be accessed conveniently using the STAC standard.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Examples from CloudFerro demonstrating access to their data catalogue might be useful, since the official STAC documentation is a bit sparse CloudFerro's documentation is still hard to navigate, since there seem to be two almost similar sources, https://wekeo.docs.cloudferro.com/ and the https://creodias.eu knowledge base. However, it was quite difficult to find the relevant things using the search function of the knowledge base. The session length of CloudFerro's OpenStack environment is very short and requires the user to login almost every hour if idle. Since experiments can take easily as long as an hour, this can become tedious. Given the 2FA, a longer session length, such as a day might be reasonable and more convenient.
Ease of use of the resources	The documentation on OpenStack and how to setup/rescale VMs has improved a lot at CREODIAS.	No new suggestions
Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case	During the development phase the flexibility of the OpenStack environment was immensely helpful because we had full control over the setup and could adjust resources to our needs. However, during the upscaling phase, it had the disadvantage that we had to implement the	For upscaling a methodology, a queue-based system like SLURM would be more convenient because the user does not have to deal with managing resources, and processes can easily be batched and parallelised.

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	<i>batch processing ourselves, as well as manage the resources manually.</i>	
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support from the providers</i>	<i>No new feedback</i>	<i>No new suggestions</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction of the service/resource</i>	<i>While CloudFerro's documentation on how to use their OpenStack environment has improved greatly, with many relevant examples, the documentation could be easier to find. Specifically, the https://creodias.eu knowledge base, since https://wekeo.docs.cloudferro.com/ follows the common read the docs standards and contains all important examples. However, the existence of the second link could be better advertised.</i>	

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Table 9. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: SAR on the fly

Functionality	<p>Deploy GPU resources to process Sentinel-1 Level 1 Single Look Complex to Analysis Ready Data, in particular coherence, for use in land use monitoring, using the ALUs open source toolbox.</p> <p>Main achievements. Set up of robust batch procedure to run ALUs coherence processor on historic Sentinel-1 SLC archive on the CDSE (previously CREODIAS) and actual data. Generated more than 10,000 12-day coherence images for the entire Ukraine territory for the period March 2019 - now. The data is used in thematic use case in agriculture, forestry and war impact assessment. The outputs are shared on public cloud platforms, both eo4ua.org and Google Earth Engine.</p>		
Integration status			
<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>	
<p><i>The code runs as binary on a NVIDIA GPU running CUDA. Open source code and dependencies are described at:</i></p> <p><i>https://github.com/cqi-estonia-space/ALUs</i></p>	<p><i>Use case</i></p>	<p><i>Sentinel-1 SLC data.</i></p> <p><i>Provider</i></p> <p><i>Sentinel-1 SLC access is mounted on the GPU VM at /eodata</i></p>	
<p><i>The run configurations are set up in python and require local access to SRTM tiles and (remote) orbit files at</i></p> <p><i>https://scihub.copernicus.eu/gnss/</i></p>	<p><i>Use case</i></p>	<p><i>Improvement suggestions from users</i></p>	
Feedback			
<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>	
<p><i>Speed of access to resources and data</i></p>	<p><i>CPU based coherence processing is about 15x slower (when fully optimized) than GPU processing. The current GPU performance requires around 33 seconds for a full scene. The transfer of the data from the /eodata archive (s3fs) to memory takes around 30 seconds. Some speed gains can be achieved by parallel transfers and/or distributing the</i></p>	<p><i>Improvement suggestions from users</i></p>	

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	<i>workflow over multiple GPU instances (not tried). Archive access has improved in speed over the course of the project.</i>				
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>The use of the resources requires Linux VM configuration skills, NVIDIA driver configuration (which is a major nuisance due to frequent updates), python skills to configure batches and monitor run time processes. Docker configuration is optional. All processes are cli based via ssh.</i>				
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>The setup is fully appropriate for expert use of public cloud resources. There is no GUI. The ALUs developers are in talks with CREODIAS/CDSE to configure the software into an orderable service. This would replace/complement the existing CREODIAS orderable service which runs on CPU (and which is considerably slower than GPU runs).</i>				
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>The application is specific to infrastructure that combines high-end GPUs with direct access to the Copernicus archive. The fact that this infrastructure is federated makes it much easier to share outputs with thematic application users. We have shown this by sharing outputs on eo4ua.org (samba mounted S3 bucket) and Google Earth Engine (via Google Cloud using gsutil).</i>				
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>ALUs development has been supported by European Space Agency funding. This project has contributed by formulating several functional requirements. Some, e.g., the integration of the Copernicus DEM, have been realized in the course of the project. GPU processing in Earth Observation has a much wider potential, however, but requires sustained development support. This project has been instrumental in demonstrating its potential at a limited scale. Further integration in Copernicus processing chains on CDSE need to be stimulated.</i>				
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>Support has been provided at different levels. The C-SCALE project has been highly effective in providing access to the resources and in the guidance of the project. Most infrastructure related issues were resolved via the CloudFerro (CREODIAS) technical staff, both for resource issues (resolving an accounting issue) and technical backstopping (problems with unshelving the GPU instance via</i>				

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openstack).

*Overall satisfaction
with C-SCALE services
and support*

Excellent (10 on a scale from 1-10)

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Table 10. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: SPOTLIGHT

Functionality	<p>Developments driven by human actions (e.g., political, economic) may be rapid but can have long-term effects on the ecological environment. An example is the loss of agricultural activities shortly after the crisis started in Syria in 2011; a similar situation may be expected in Afghanistan, which has a lot of irrigated agriculture or may expand illicit crop cultivation such as poppy.</p> <p>The spatial resolution and acquisition frequency makes Copernicus datasets (in particular Sentinel-2) a perfect monitoring tool for such situations. However, using such datasets are still cumbersome for end-users in government organisations, NGOs, but also for scientists and researchers who aim for rapid prototyping. Often, data need to be accessed file-based, and algorithms might still need to be prepared. The semantic EO data cube has its first worldwide implementation in the Sen2Cube.at system (http://sen2cube.at), which is developed by the Department of Geoinformatics – Z_GIS of the University of Salzburg and the Spatial Services GmbH and is currently hosted at the EODC in Vienna. Sen2Cube.at has shown in various applications (e.g., agricultural monitoring) that it is a tool which can bridge this gap by providing semantically enriched data in a fact base together with a knowledgebase of pre-defined semantic models, ready for querying. To fully use the potential of the semantic EO data cube exists outside specific narrow time intervals and area-of-interest, it is necessary to upscale them. This will facilitate analyses on larger areas require flexible and scalable computational capacities that are suitable for Copernicus Big Data Analytics.</p> <p>Main achievements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upscaling of analyses in semantic EO data cube. • Establishing new data cubes with an area in Afghanistan as an example. 		
Integration status			
<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>	
Sentinel-2 L1C data	Provider		
Docker	Provider		
Feedback			
<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>	
Speed of access to resources and data	Access is fast.		
Ease of use of the resources	It is required to have substantial knowledge about IT administration and Linux.		

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There will always be a trade-off between ease-of-use and available functions/features. For this use-case a set of preconfigured but limited features were not applicable.

Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case *The virtual machines work fine but require administrative tasks from users. Container-based applications can benefit from a container orchestrator as well.*

Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure *Due to 100% container-based architecture the application can run on the federated infrastructure.*

Missing functionality / resources *Not applicable.*

Effectiveness of support *There are no blocking issues and any issues that occurred in the beginning were resolved quickly.*

Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support *Regular meetings, in particular in the beginning were helpful and all issues that occurred in the beginning were resolved quickly. The development of the use-case happened in close collaboration with several options to present at several events.*

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Table 11. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: NC4EC

Functionality	<p>This use case deals with the operational and in real-time solar energy nowcasting from zero to six hours ahead at 15-minute intervals for the whole Austrian domain. To this direction Earth Observation data and methods were exploited including geostationary satellite retrievals, ground-truth measurements for validation and modelled information in conjunction with fast radiative transfer simulations, artificial intelligence and cloud computing services.</p> <p>Main achievements. The new European Energy Target Model has as a main scope the energy market liberalization and the creation of a single competitive electricity market. The main characteristic of this model has to do with the continuous intraday energy trading, so the operational exploitation of Earth Observations in energy planning and management will be able to provide accurate solar energy information in terms of nowcasts, crucial in the energy market, where on-the-spot energy prices are defined by supply and demand equilibriums. As a result, this use case is able to support the energy suppliers with accurate estimations for the distributed solar energy production, a knowledge that will provide them with a comprehensive advantage with clear economic benefits.</p>		
Integration status			
Dependency	Implemented by	Status	
<i>Eumetsat data retrieval in real-time.</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>A dedicated in-house antenna and receiver were installed for the purposes of this use case.</i>	
<i>Computational expensive radiative transfer software.</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>Use of pre-calculated look-up-tables in order to speed-up the processing chain and reduce the cloud computing requirements.</i>	
Feedback			
Category	Feedback	Improvement suggestions from users	
<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Limited or no access to the Eumetsat SAFNWC data. The CPU availability is not fully secured 24/7.</i>	<i>Inclusion of these data sources. Ensure a minimum continuously available CPU per VM for seamless service operations.</i>	
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>The VMs and the programming in OpenStack environment is an advantage for the optimum exploitation of resources but require from the users to get familiar.</i>	<i>An analytical tutorial with examples will be helpful for the users.</i>	
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use</i>	<i>In theory the available technology is adequate in order to implement this use case but in practice is not mature enough for complex operational projects that require the 100% of the requested resources</i>	<i>Use and introduction of well-functioning protocols for dynamic VM optimization (similarly to the AWS).</i>	

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<i>case</i>	<i>24/7.</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>The use case could be easily replicated to any region and extend depending only to the available computing resources.</i>
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>The efficient provision of GPU cuda cores programming and the related functionalities (distributed computing, ray tracing, etc).</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>The support is sufficient but not extensively tested.</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support</i>	<i>A promising service which could be much more mature through numerous use cases of varying complexity and demandingness.</i>

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Table 12. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: G-PeT

Functionality	<p>Porting a selection of our remote sensing algorithms to GPU hardware, which could benefit from this specific hardware architecture. Running tests to compare CPU/GPU implementations and present the potential benefits in a workshop.</p> <p>Main achievements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjusting the existing algorithm implementations so they would run on the GPU, but without too much maintenance overhead. • Analysing performance and profiling reports to compare CPU and GPU hardware. • Investigating different data architecture to better benefit from the high throughput of the GPU and developing a deeper understanding of the hardware. • Investigating compute per kilowatt hour and potential cost savings. • Presented these findings and how to achieve them using some of the tested algorithms as an example in a workshop.
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Integration status

<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>
<i>Sigma0 20m data</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>A comprehensive example set has been delivered from EODC to GRNET which could be easily accessed.</i>
<i>NVIDIA device</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>CloudFerro provided access to their cloud GPU via a VM which had CUDA and all necessary drivers installed.</i>
<i>CPU cluster</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>GRNET provided us with access to their HPC cluster to perform CPU tests and analytics.</i>
<i>Python libraries</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>Python dependencies have been installed on the VM using conda environments. We also received very prompt and helpful support to setup our environment on the GRNET node.</i>

Feedback

<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>
<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Since all our resources resided locally on disk on premise, accessing the data was generally quite fast. Since GPUs are specialised on high throughput and hiding exactly such data latency, we didn't experience any issues there. The data was moved only once in bulk from EODC to GRNET, which was handled by the provider.</i>	
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>We already had a setup running on CloudFerro for a different use case, which made it quite easy to deploy our algorithms there, since we were already familiar with the environment.</i>	<i>We only had a small difficulty getting our python environment working on their compute nodes. Here an example in the documentation, on how to set up a python environment and activate on the compute node</i>

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	<i>GRNET has an easy to use SLURM interface, with which we were already comfortable with.</i>	<i>would be quite helpful, similar to the one provided to us by the support.</i>
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>Both the A6000 Nvidia GPU provided by CloudFerro, and the compute nodes provided by GRNET were appropriate hardware to do a comparison of different algorithm implementations, since they properly reflect the current environment our algorithms usually run.</i>	<i>Testing certain algorithms on a consumer grade GPU would have been interesting as well, since some methods might benefit more from the cost/power savings than from the increased compute. Additionally, consumer grade GPUs have different allocation ratio of FP32 and FP64 cores which can be beneficial for some algorithms.</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>In principle the algorithms which have been ported to CUDA can be used on any infrastructure providing CUDA devices, however, since the goal of this use case was investigating different hardware setups, reusability was not the main focus.</i>	
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>A consumer grade or low power GPU would have been interesting for certain algorithms.</i>	
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>Login setup from GRNET was fast and painless, as well as the data transfer. However, the static IP approach to login could cause problems for some users, and could also result in future problems, for instance if the setup should change on our end. Response to our difficulties with the python environment setup at GRNET was swift, and on the point. The code example provided quickly resolved the issue. This could be added to the documentation.</i>	<i>Login to GRNET: Maybe a different login procedure using 2FA or similar would be easier. Conda environment at GRNET compute nodes: Update the user documentation with the instructions shared via email.</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support</i>	<i>In general, we didn't experience any major problems, and all our issues have been resolved quickly.</i>	

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Table 13. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: TWC-SCUP

Functionality TWC-SCUP extends (=scales up) the capabilities of the commercial offering Tama WaldCursor (TWC). We want to figure out if a systematic scale up of satellite data processing (Sentinel-2) from a current average of 5 km² to an average of 50 km², while at the same time extending use from the last 12 months to now cover 60 months, is achievable by using a high performance computing centre (HPC).
Main achievements. With data volumes scaling up by a factor of 50 we had to develop new ways of how to split up data in spatial and temporal tiles, in other words, to create a data cube manageable by our WaldCursor. To use the HPC we had to get familiar with specific data processing environments such as SLURM.

Integration status

<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>
<i>Sentinel 2 data: ingesting L2A</i>	<i>Provider</i>	
<i>Application data: Area of Interest (AOI)</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
<i>eCognition software</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
<i>TWC processing software</i>	<i>Use case</i>	

Feedback

<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>
<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Provision of L2A data required several weeks, also due to the size of the AOI and the complexity of the processing algorithms. Provision of HPC resources: whilst technically straightforward, the real bottleneck was getting us trained up.</i>	
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>Use of the commercial Virtual Machine required transition to a new environment, referred to as OpenStack. This required several weeks. Use of the HPC environment required training and some degree of 'playing' to get familiar with - which in our case also took a couple of weeks.</i>	
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use</i>	<i>Whilst our commercial set-up is tailored to Windows environments, we had to get used to be hosted for this use case by a Linux environment. Technologically this looks all fine, except for eCognition (which we</i>	

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<i>case</i>	<i>haven't explored in this project).</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>We are still processing (status as of June 7th, 2023). Preliminary results look fine.</i>
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>Not applicable.</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>We were in good use of support, both for the OpenStack migration as well as the HPC setup phase. Once the initial phase was accomplished, support was highly effective.</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support</i>	<i>Great team and great support. No reservations.</i>

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Table 14. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: LOST-Salvage

Functionality	<p>The objective of LOST-Salvage is to pilot operational support for salvage operations at sea using Lagrangian Ocean Search Targets (LOST). To this end the use case will download global wind and ocean current hindcast and forecast data on a daily basis, which are used as input data for LOST. The ambition is to enable stakeholders to run LOST simulations anywhere in the global ocean. The ambition is to set up a simple dashboard to facilitate this, either via https://streamlit.io/, or via Jupyter Notebooks combined with https://voila.readthedocs.io/.</p> <p>Completed issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to computation resources • Docker and Jupyter Notebooks set up and working (i.e., interoperability and collaborative development) • LOST simulations can run easily upon cloning repo. • Created and attached separate storage volume with support from C-SCALE • Created functionality to get global ocean surface currents from CMEMS and GlobCurrent via opendap. <p>Working on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Getting global wind products • Workflow to fetch global products daily • Interactive maps and analytics 	
Integration status		
<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>
<i>EGI Check-in to access cloud IaaS</i>	<i>Provider</i>	<i>User can access provider's OpenStack and deploy VMs.</i>
<i>Global ocean surface current and wind data</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>Developing scripts and workflow to get data</i>
<i>Notebooks via Docker</i>	<i>Use case / Provider</i>	<i>User installed Docker. C-SCALE support created network port for egress to use Notebooks via Docker on VM.</i>
<i>Python libraries and JupyterHub</i>	<i>Use case</i>	<i>Docker container including dependencies and instructions to build the docker image have been implemented by the use case. Support provided by C-SCALE.</i>
Feedback		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>

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<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Speed of access to computational resources was great. Accessing data has become a user activity, which is a bit disappointing but understandable given available expertise and resources in C-SCALE.</i>
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>Computational resources are easy to use if you know OpenStack. There is pretty comprehensive documentation and support available through C-SCALE.</i>
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>Have not made enough progress on implementing the use case to comment.</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>Have not made enough progress on implementing the use case to comment.</i>
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>Have not made enough progress on implementing the use case to comment.</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>So far, the support has been very effective, issues get resolved very quickly.</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support</i>	<i>Overall, pretty satisfied with C-SCALE services and support. What's disappointing is that the user is responsible for ensuring the data they need are available on the infrastructure.</i>

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Table 15. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: GLTFCA

Functionality	<p>The GLTFCA project use case centred around the detection of forest degradation and regrowth across an area of around 10 million ha in Central Mozambique. The use case is based on using the Anomaly Vegetation Change Detection (AVOCADO) algorithm to capture disturbance and regrowth over periods of various lengths, ranging up to 20 years.</p> <p>There was limited time to come to significant results, but we are still hopeful to achieve this before the end of June. Our first run was based solely on running through a number of vegetation indices derived from Landsat images across the study area. We were hopeful to also include some SAR calibrated NDVI time series data to the mix, after our first run and compare results.</p>
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Integration status

<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>
<i>Large Virtual Machine with Ubuntu 20.04 pre-installed.</i>	<i>Provider</i>	

Feedback

<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>
<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Since our use case have not explored much of the data on offer, I cannot comment on this - we were hoping to explore this once we completed our first run of the data. The speed of resources such as internet connection was good.</i>	
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>Much time was spent on getting workflows right and this is probably due to the inexperience of myself using large cloud infrastructure. OpenStack was complicated to work with for creating a VM but thankfully support generated a VM for our use case on request (support was excellent by the way).</i>	
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>Highly appropriate.</i>	
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>	

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*federated
infrastructure*

*Missing functionality /
resources*

Not applicable

*Effectiveness of
support*

Support was very much effective and excellent.

*Overall satisfaction
with C-SCALE services
and support*

C-SCALE services are great and high satisfaction levels with support and the services offered. We regret not having the time to explore more of the opportunities and services provided by C-SCALE useful to our use case.

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Table 16. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: NivarIA

Functionality	<p>Easy scale-up of agronomic and environmental algorithms to big datasets via no-code tool. These datasets are built from openEO imagery sources and collected in the designed data warehouse in order to be easily exploited by AI models defined by end users.</p> <p>Main achievements.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The definition of a scalable architecture of a solution regarding the data ingestion, aggregation and consumption in AI frameworks within a cloud ecosystem. Specifically, it allows to develop the major part of the workflow within a single cluster and thus reducing bottlenecks around data moves. 2. The implementation of a data orchestration layer that allows ingesting and modelling data from third parties through openEO stack.
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Integration status

<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>
<i>Kubernetes cluster via Terraform and KubeSpray</i>	<i>Use case and provider</i>	
<i>Prefect 2</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
<i>Cloud Native PG</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
<i>MinIO</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
<i>PostgresML as PostgreSQL extension</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
<i>MindsDB as AI layer on top of the database</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
<i>dbt Cloud as in-house data modelling tool</i>	<i>Use case</i>	

Feedback

<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>
<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Blazing fast. EODC was quite efficient in resource allocation when demanded.</i>	
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>OpenStack has a steep learning curve, and it complicates the required efforts and resources for the deployment. The help from EODC support was quite valuable.</i>	

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Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case *Great flexibility thanks to Kubernetes application deployment.*

Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure *Quite useable up to date.*

Missing functionality / resources *We are missing a default load balancer in OpenStack cloud.*

Effectiveness of support *10 out of 10.*

Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support *10 out of 10.*

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Table 17. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: African Rainfall

Functionality	<p>The African Rainfall Project is a crowd computing project of the World Community Grid (https://www.worldcommunitygrid.org/). Through BOINC, a numerical weather model (WRF) is run on the computers of thousands of volunteers. The simulations cover all of sub-Saharan Africa at a one kilometre resolution for a full year, which is unique.</p> <p>Main achievements. The African climate is governed by monsoons. Rainfall is mainly (>80%) produced through localized convective storms. Such storms are difficult to reproduce at a coarse resolution. By going to the very fine resolution of 1 km, convective storms can be resolved.</p>
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Integration status

<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>

Feedback

<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>
<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>As the resources physically overlap with those from a previous national project, access to resources and data are well taken care of.</i>	
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>Because the processing that is needed is very limited, the resources needed are relatively simple as well and work well.</i>	
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>For the African Rainfall Project, the technology fits very well as it allows storage on different media (tape and disk) of all our data.</i>	
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>The African Rainfall Project only started to use C-SCALE resources recently (March 2023). This was essential for the success of the project and also provided seamless bridging over time.</i>	
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>Not applicable.</i>	
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>Support has been effective, especially through the SURF liaison.</i>	

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Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support

Overall satisfaction is high with little problem encountered along the way.

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Table 18. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: pangeo-reliance

Functionality	<p>In most places on the planet vegetation thrives, this is known as “greening Earth”. However, in certain regions, especially in the Arctic, there are areas exhibiting a browning trend. Here we focus on the Troms and Finnmark counties in northern Norway to assess the extent of the phenomenon and any link with local environmental conditions. Being able to accurately predict areas where Arctic browning will likely occur (or has occurred recently) is useful for indigenous people in the Arctic e.g., Sami people who live from reindeer herding. It can help them to better manage local resources, including the number of reindeers they can have.</p> <p>Main achievements. We used combined information derived from Sentinel-2 data by the Copernicus Global Land Service (Global Land Cover) and meteorological data (ERA5-Land precipitation and 2m air temperature) to build, train and validate a feed forward neural network able to forecast moss and lichen fractional cover.</p>		
Integration status			
	<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>
	<i>Pangeo/ml-notebook container (https://hub.docker.com/r/pangeo/ml-notebook/tags)</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
	<i>Nvidia Tensorflow container (https://catalog.ngc.nvidia.com/orgs/nvidia/containers/tensorflow)</i>	<i>Use case</i>	
Feedback			
	<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>
	<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Access to the CESNET GPU VM was reasonably fast, however the performance of the alternative resource (Tesla T4) and the limited amount of GPU memory (15360MiB) was an issue, especially in the exploratory phases of the project. So, we had to reconsider the problem and simplify the model, moving from the 100 ×100m grid of the GLC to the 9 ×9km of Era5-Land and deriving statistical values.</i>	
	<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>We had no issues with the use of the resources and had already experience with OpenStack from CESNET.</i>	
	<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use</i>	<i>The limited compute power did not allow us to solve the actual use case we had originally defined, but a simplified problem instead. However, our simplified model nonetheless captured the main features in the</i>	

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<i>case</i>	<i>temperature and precipitation pattern leading to the depletion of moss and lichen in this arctic region.</i>
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>The federated infrastructure was well suited to collaboratively work on the use case.</i>
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>More powerful GPUs (than the Tesla T4) represent an enormous leap in performance and efficiency, in this kind of AI applications.</i>
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>Support was responsive and did its best to find an alternative solution when C-SCALE had to pause the resource allocation and we switched to CESNET.</i>
<i>Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support</i>	<i>Support was great, although we did not get the overall service that we were led to expect (i.e., access to powerful GPUs close to the data).</i>

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Table 19. Functionality, integration status and user feedback from Use Case: pangeo-eosc

Functionality	<p>Pangeo Europe Use Case aims at streamlining deployments on EOSC of the Pangeo ecosystem for big data geosciences e.g., with access to additional parallel computing capabilities (for instance through Dask Gateway). Different needs emerged from the Pangeo Europe communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • analysing deforestation patterns on the regional scale in Mexico with the use of Sentinel-1 time series; • vegetation analysis with Copernicus Global Land Services S3TOC from VITO; • better understand vegetation browning in Troms and Finnmark (Norway); • Streamlined access to climate datasets such as CMIP6, ERA5, ERA5-Land for climate data analysis; • geolocating fish using biologging data and ocean sea surface temperature and pressure data; • Pangeo Training Infrastructure as a Service. <p>A Pangeo JupyterHub was deployed with 4 different kernels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pangeo Notebook; • Machine Learning Pangeo notebook with GPU-enabled tensorflow2; • Machine learning Pangeo notebook with GPU-enabled pytorch; • Datascience Notebook with Python, R and Julia. <p>For this deployment, object storage was also provided through MinIO.</p> <p>This deployment was used to facilitate the reproducibility of the papers as part of the CI2023 reproducibility challenge. More information is available on the Reproducibility challenge website⁴²: 24 people were registered to the reproducibility challenge and grouped in 6 different teams. The deployment was not used by all the teams and the overall feedback was the difficulty to create buckets (minIO). Once created, the teams were satisfied with the resources even though some users reported that the compute resources were very slow.</p> <p>A BinderHub deployment with Dask Gateway has also been deployed within the C-SCALE project for the Pangeo Community. It is a very good step forward as it would meet most of the Pangeo community needs. However, because of the lack of time, only few tests were done. The dask cluster was accessible through the created BinderHub but the image used was not the Pangeo notebook image (but a default Python Jupyter notebook image with very little packages). Here the Pangeo community needs to decide what would be needed e.g., BinderHub with Pangeo notebook and dask cluster or BinderHub with dask cluster only.</p>
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⁴² <https://github.com/c-scale-community/workflow-coastal-hydrowaq/pull/52>

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Integration status

<i>Dependency</i>	<i>Implemented by</i>	<i>Status</i>
<i>Kubernetes</i>	<i>Provider</i>	
<i>BinderHub</i>	<i>Provider</i>	
<i>Dask Gateway</i>	<i>Provider</i>	
<i>MinIO object store</i>	<i>Provider</i>	

Feedback

<i>Category</i>	<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Improvement suggestions from users</i>
<i>Speed of access to resources and data</i>	<i>Speed of access to data was good. Some hardware was not always the most efficient (for instance GPUs were not the most recent and powerful) but thanks to the deployments most of the work planned were realized.</i>	
<i>Ease of use of the resources</i>	<i>pangeo-eosc was used for a Reproducibility challenge that ran over the month of May. This was an opportunity to advertise further EOSC and C-SCALE.</i>	
<i>Appropriateness of the technology used to implement the use case</i>	<i>The Pangeo technologies were familiar to all users involved in the Pangeo Use Case. For the Reproducibility challenge additional training was provided.</i>	
<i>Resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure</i>	<i>Thanks to the use of the Pangeo ecosystem, users can prototype on their laptops and then scale on the C-SCALE infrastructure.</i>	
<i>Missing functionality / resources</i>	<i>Still some work to be done with BinderHub with dask cluster.</i>	
<i>Effectiveness of support</i>	<i>Very good support from the C-SCALE team. Lots of webinars organised on different topics which was very much appreciated. All the webinars were recorded which allowed more users from the Pangeo community</i>	

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to benefit from them.

Overall satisfaction with C-SCALE services and support

We are very satisfied with the support. The C-SCALE compute were overall much smaller than anticipated and spread over several providers which was not ideal for us. The Pangeo deployments were very well streamlined and very quickly ready to use which was very good.

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